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Prevention of Deviant Behavior of Children by Means of Socio-Cultural Activities

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Abstract

Prevention of deviant behavior of children is to monitor risk factors that can have a negative impact on the child. Above all, family control is necessary because it is in the family that values, behavioral stereotypes are laid, the emotional sphere of the child is formed. Scientists of various sciences repeatedly turn to the problem of deviant behavior, but so far there is no single approach to its definition. Deviant behavior is interpreted as antisocial behavior, as behavior violating any social, cultural, ethical or legal norms as behavior deviating from mental health norms, i.e. overt or covert psychopathology.

The aim of the study is a theoretical study of the methodology and the development of recommendations for their use in pedagogical activities for the prevention of deviant behavior of children by means of socio-cultural activities.

The study is based on theoretical analysis of philosophical, psychological, sociological, pedagogical, cultural, reference literature. The research methodology used is the survey of children, teachers, and organizers of leisure activities. The stating, formative and control experiments were performed to develop the recommendations. The authors also designed socio-cultural programs, introducing spiritual and moral values through theatrical programs.

Developed theatrical programs for the prevention of deviant behavior of children showed an increase in children's interest in positive communication, the desire to engage in creativity in their free time, and to study literature. This confirms that the prevention of deviant behavior of children is effective when using socio-cultural means. The study proves that social and cultural activities can solve the problem of prevention of children's deviant behavior consequently develop children's moral values and spiritual preferences due to various ways and methods of influence on the personality.

Keywords: prevention, socio-cultural activity, behavior, personality, creative process, spiritual and moral education.

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Introduction

It is known that activity is an integral process of personal development. Accordingly, we can think that socialization as a property of the personality is in the process of social activity as a result of activity.

The developing process of multiplication of the role of informal, non-institutional factors that form the personality and, first of all, factors of an open microsocial environment, could not but affect the state of psychological, social, cultural development of children. The theme is actual, as in the process of social and cultural activities, upbringing, there is a transmission of historical and cultural experiences from generation to generation (Akmurzиеva & Dubchenkova, 2019)

From the point of view of many researchers, cultural activity is an activity aimed at the creation, preservation and dissemination of cultural values and the introduction of various layers of the population to them. Social and cultural activities can be defined as a multi-functional sphere of activity, one of the components of social work. Its object is organization of meaningful and rational leisure of people, the development and satisfaction of their cultural needs, the creation of conditions for the self-realization of each separate person, the disclosure of the abilities, self-improvement and amateur creativity in the framework of free time (Dubchenkova, 2016).

The main feature of society at the modern stage of development is not only social instability but also the destruction of traditional institutions of socialization, change of the standard ways of minor's self-realization. Correction of existing forms of upbringing and development of minors is required. Therefore, we can conclude that the importance of conduction of active purposeful preventive work like in secondary schools and institutions of additional education, highlighting the problem of deviant behavior.

The various definitions are used to denote deviant behavior: delinquent behavior, deviant behavior, asocial behavior, etc. in social, psychological and pedagogical researches. The deviation is one of the sides of the phenomenon of changeability, which is related to a person and the world around him. Changeability in the social sphere is always associated with activity and expressed in human behavior, which is an interaction with the environment, mediated by external and internal activities of the adolescent. In this regard, the behavior of children is usually distinguished as normal and deviant.

Normal (adequate, adaptive) behavior of children assumes interaction with the micro-community, which adequately meets the needs and opportunities of the development and socialization. Hence, deviant behavior can be characterized as the interaction of a child with a micro-community, which violates his development and socialization by the lack of adequate consideration of the environment of the features of

his personality and manifests in behavioral opposition to established moral and legal social norms (Palatkina, 2015).

So, deviant behavior is a type of deviant behavior connected with the violation of age-appropriate norms and rules of behavior, which is characterized by microsocial relationships (family, school) and small age and gender social groups. Typical expressions of deviant behavior are situationally caused child and adolescent behavioral reactions, such as manifestation, aggression, challenge, unauthorized and systematic deviation from school or work; systematic leaving from home and vagrancy, drunkenness and alcoholism of children and adolescents; early narcosis and connected with asocial actions; antisocial sexual actions; suicide attempts (Bondyreva, 2007).

Purpose and objectives of the study

The aim of the study is a theoretical study of the methodology and the development of recommendations for their use in pedagogical activities for the prevention of deviant behavior of children by means of socio-cultural activities.

Accordingly, we can define the main task of social and cultural activities: it consists in the need to control the processes of social adaptation and individualization of the personality of minors, in other words, over social education and development, as well as control over the realized forms of leisure activities. Social and cultural activities are aimed at optimal and functional organization of leisure for the purpose of self-improvement, moral enrichment and physical development (Palatkina, 2015).

Literature review

The works of Makarenko (1983), Belicheva (1994), Yaroshevsky (1999), Krutetsky (1972) has a significant value in this regard. Methodological basis of the research was the ideas of A. S. Makarenko about a role of staff in formation of an adolescent's personality, Titov (1996) about a role of cultural and leisure activities in the socialization of adolescents, Yaroshevsky (1999) about the importance of the club and club activity of the staff in the formation of personality, Belicheva (1994) about the importance of organizing a full communication with others to correct deviant behavior, Krutetsky (1972) about professional skills and pedagogical tools of a social teacher (Mendelevich, 2005).

Makarenko (1983) thinks that the involvement of children in cultural and leisure activities is a form of training in socially approving behavior.

Thus, the following reasons allow us to consider social and cultural activities as a basic method of preventive work with minors who have deviant behavior:

- social and cultural environment is particularly attractive for children and adolescents due to the possibility of showing themselves as a subject of socially significant activity;
- social and cultural activities are the motive of creation, preservation and propagation of cultural values;
- social and cultural activities is provided with the necessary tools of influence on the subconscious and behavior of children and adolescents (Volkov, 2008).

Methodology

Theoretical analysis of philosophical, psychological, sociological, pedagogical, cultural, reference literature; conversations, questionnaires; survey of children and teachers, organizers of leisure; staging, formative and control experiments; designing socio-cultural programs, introducing spiritual and moral values through theatrical programs (Sidorov, 2008).

First of all, the effectiveness of the educational influences of cultural and leisure activities on children largely depend on the choice of forms as an important means of expressing the content of the activity. The form is a combination of ways and means of organizing the process of cultural and leisure activities due to the content (Bondyрева, 2007).

Organizational forms of work with children should be aimed at the development of their cognitive interests and abilities. It is important to note that childhood is a period of development characterized by significant changes in all sides of the personality-the psyche, physiology, relationships when the child subjectively enters into relations with the adult world. Therefore, only a differentiated approach in the choice of certain forms can provide the effectiveness of their influence. One of these forms is the art form. It includes messages about the most active events, which are combined in order of importance and presented imaginatively using emotional means of influence.

This form can include mass performances, evenings of rest, show performances, spectacles, literary evenings, creative meetings with famous people.

The above-mentioned forms as evenings of rest show performances will arouse special interest among children in two cases: if they are imbued with the spirit of competition and imbued with deep lyricism. The unrealized tenderness of the soul and the desire to compete with peers in everything are features of difficult children (Bondyрева, 2007).

Balls and carnivals are a bright form of organization of spectacular performances. They are dedicated to the most important events in the life of a child, but, unfortunately, these forms are now rarely used, because for such holidays you need beautiful costumes, which many leisure institutions can not give.

Educative forms include lectures, conversations, debates, conferences and excursions. For example, in the process of participation in a debate, discussion, children learn not only something new but also learn to form their own point of view (Volkov, 2008).

There is such a form as a cognitive and entertaining in the practice of cultural and leisure activities. It is greatly important for adolescent children. During this period the character of game activity changes, the game loses its "fabulousness", "mystery" and the cognitive significance of the game comes to the fore.

The greatest effect is given by forms taken from the TV screen, for example, cognitive and entertaining games "Brain-ring", "What? Where? When?".

The most interesting form of leisure activity for children is a disco club. There are two types of discos: educative and educational (disco-club), dancing and entertaining (disco-dance floor). If the first case has a clear objective, which is followed by some theme, so, the second does not have any objective. Thus, the creation of a disco club contributes to the development of musical taste (Andreeva, 2005).

Social and practical forms play a special role in the development of spiritual principles of the child's personality. Taking into account the social and practical interests of children, you can create rooms of psychological unloading, sections, clubs for physical culture and sports, sewing training and technical creativity.

"Several priority positions can be identified in the purposeful setting of cultural and leisure activities, among them:

- increasing the degrees of independence of the child from preschool age, adolescent, adult in the choice and realization of leisure needs, their ability to control their free time and more effectively solve the problems of leisure;
- creating conditions in which both children and adults can instill leisure initiative and creative opportunities to the maximum level" (Volkov, 2008).

It would be possible to identify the main directions of cultural and leisure activities, which are necessary for the upbringing and self-education of children. One of the main directions of cultural and leisure

institutions is civil upbringing which forms a scientific outlook and develops a child's civil activity in the pedagogical process. You can use such forms as lectures, conversations and debates in civil education. The approximate theme of lectures: "The Fatherland at the turn of the century", "The historical past of our Motherland"; theme of discussions: "What a hero of our time – he is", etc.

In this case, the use of visual technical means will be able to give an emotional color and expressiveness that will cause the greatest interest in children.

Another important direction of cultural and leisure activities is labor upbringing. The purpose of labor upbringing is to assist in the professional orientation of adolescent children. Meetings with representatives of various professions, excursions in production sites where children get acquainted with representatives of various professions, technical clubs of modeling have a great importance (Palatkina & Podlipalin, 2019).

The next direction of cultural and leisure activities is the formation of a personality with high moral consciousness and behavior-moral upbringing. The principle of moral upbringing is the principle of upbringing on positive examples. Moral upbringing in the club is carried out in the sphere of communication with peers through the system of moral education (ethical conversations, debates, meetings with interesting people). When developing a personality, it is important to take into account the ability to understand correctly the beautiful things in all their various expressions.

Therefore, one of the main sides of cultural and leisure activities are aesthetic upbringing. The objective is to develop the ability to evaluate, perceive and approve the beautiful things in life and art from the universal positions of spiritual heritage. The pedagogical task of cultural institutions is to involve children in their activities by organization of show performances, creative beauty contests ("miss - spring", "mister-show"), meetings with musicians, fashion designers, poets, visit of exhibitions and much more.

The direction to physical upbringing determines the development and strengthening of the health, physical abilities of children and adolescents. One of the tasks of physical upbringing is to educate the will and character, the moral qualities and aesthetic tastes. Thus, the physical is connected with moral and aesthetic upbringing (Palatkina, 2015).

The development of the given direction is supported by the organization of clubs, sports sections, meetings with people who are directly related to sports (coaches, masters of sports).

Thus, all these directions of cultural and leisure activities are interconnected and interdependent.

In the process of the directed upbringing of the child's personality, on the one hand, there is spiritual and moral development, on the other, there is a kind of differentiation of abilities, various interests and needs are revealed, the child's socialization occurs, which has a positive direction.

The modern state of the pedagogical process convinces that the activity needs a more intense ethical direction, bringing to the fore social problems aimed at harmonizing relations between children, satisfying the individual and society as a whole (Dubchenkova, 2016).

Thus, analyzing the general characteristic of deviant behavior of minor children, and also the conditions and reasons for the occurrence of deviations in behavior, we came to the conclusion that among the various social factors that determine asocial behavior, we can distinguish such as:

1. An individual factor, which acts on the level of psychobiological prerequisites of asocial behavior that makes it difficult for a social adaption of an individual.
2. The psychological and pedagogical factor that appears in the defects of school and family upbringing.
3. Social and psychological factor, which reveals the negative features of interaction of minors with their closest environment in the family, on the street, in the educational team.
4. The personal factor that appears in the actively selective attitude of the individual to the preferred environment of communication, the norms and values of his environment, to the pedagogical influences of the family, school, and society.
5. A social factor is determined by the social and socio-economic conditions of the existence of a society (Akmurzieva & Dubchenkova, 2019).

Analyzing the above, it becomes obvious that the early prevention of minors offenses should be considered not from the position of social control but from the position of prevention of the process of de-socialization (prevention and correction of social deviations and social maladaptation of children and management of the process of socialization of minors).

The social and cultural, cultural and leisure activities are one of the most important means of optimization of the social and cultural environment of the individual and get the opportunities of satisfaction`s needs of the individual and society as a whole (Kpeiberg, 2001).

Results

Developed theatrical programs for the prevention of deviant behavior of children showed an increase in children's interest in positive communication, a desire to engage in creativity in their free time, to study literature. This confirms that the prevention of deviant behavior of children is effective when using socio-cultural means. So, exactly how the means of socio-cultural activity carry the creation, preservation, dissemination of cultural values and the involvement of various segments of the population (Palatkina, 2015).

Discussions

The use of socio-cultural activities for the prevention of deviant behavior of children, it is necessary to build on a multicultural, environmental and systematic approach, and take into account pedagogical principles based on the specifics of age, gender, ethnic, mental characteristics of children, a special approach to the child, which consists in one or another need for a specific creative and leisure detail (Palatkina & Podlipalin, 2019).

Conclusion

Thus, deviant behavior is a type of deviant behavior associated with the violation of age-appropriate norms and rules of behavior characteristic of microsocial relationships (family, school) and small age and gender social groups. Typical manifestations of deviant behavior are situationally determined child and adolescent behavioral reactions, such as demonstration, aggression, challenge, unauthorized and systematic deviation from study or work; systematic home leave and vagrancy, alcoholism and alcoholism in children and adolescents; early anesthesia and related antisocial actions; sexual antisocial activities; suicide attempts. Socio-cultural activity, respectively, can be defined as a unifying multifunctional sphere of activity, one of the components of social work (Palatkina, 2015).

In conclusion, we can emphasize the main role of social and cultural activities in the prevention of deviant behavior of children, which consists of the inclusion of minors in a socially approved system of relationships, the finding and usage of their capabilities, which contributes to the successful socialization of children components of social work.

The role of social and cultural activities in the prevention of deviant behavior is fully justified. It fulfils the mission of object's transformation of educative influence in a subject of social and cultural creativity. The social and cultural activity is an educative activity; it has a human-making character, focuses on the person,

on the exhaustive disclosure of the spiritual potential inherent. The social and cultural relations and connections between people, people themselves and the real reality surrounding them are changed in the process of this activity (Kpeiberg, 2001).

Social and cultural activities can solve the problem of prevention of children's deviant behavior, change behavior, thus, consequently, alter their worldview, and develop activity, independence, moral values and spiritual preferences due to various ways and methods of influence on the personality.

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